

TAILORED ZINC OXIDE INTERPHASE IN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL PERFORMANCE ACROSS STRAIN RATES

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ABSTRACT

Fiber reinforced composites for ballistic applications are usually designed with a weak fiber-matrix interface to allow easy debonding and higher energy absorption. However, such designs possess poor structural performance and suffer from easy delamination. For that, many applications that require simultaneously high structural and ballistic performance require the use of multi-components systems to satisfy both requirements. Thus, the ability to tailor the fiber-matrix interface for optimal performance under both static and dynamic loading conditions would allow for the fabrication of single component multifunctional composite systems. In this work, the use of zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles and nanowires interphases to obtain the desired interfacial properties as a function of strain rates is demonstrated. Using variable strain rate pullout, the ZnO nanowires grown on the surfaces of carbon fibers are shown to produce more than 80% increase in interfacial shear strength at quasi-static strain rates, and more than 50% decrease in interfacial shear strength at high loading rates. The resulting interfacial behavior is attributed to the viscoelastic effects in the polymer matrix. At low strain rates, a functional gradient is introduced between the interphase and the matrix, reducing stress concentrations. Under dynamic loading, the increase in matrix stiffness restricts the gradient's effectiveness and results in the brittle failure of the ceramic interphase. These results indicate the ability of ZnO nanowires and nanoparticles to allow for the design of fiber-matrix interfaces with tailored properties and to enable multifunctional composites of optimal performance under both static and dynamic loading conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The unique properties of fiber reinforced composites, such as high specific strength and light weight, makes them ideal candidates for ballistic protection against blasts, projectiles, and fragments [1]. Composites used in such applications are typically designed to have a weakly adhered fiber-matrix, promoting debonding and allowing for impact energy to be absorbed by the tough fibers and dissipated through inter-yarn friction [2]. However, these interfacial properties result in poor structural performance under static loading conditions. Given the inability of tailoring the fiber-matrix interface to simultaneously meet structural and ballistic performance requirements, many applications resort to using multi-component systems that lead to an increase in weight and usage complexity, while reducing user's flexibility [3]. Therefore, highly performant multifunctional materials, under both static and dynamic loading conditions, are necessary for the integration of ballistic protection into various structures, while maintaining its lightweight, and simplicity.

Numerous techniques have been reported in order to fabricate multifunctional systems with simultaneously high ballistic and structural performance. Multi-layer structural laminates, known as composite integral armor (CIA), combined ceramic alumina tiles for ballistic protection with a thick section composite plate to act as structural backing [4,5]. However, low mass efficiency prevented its use in ground combat vehicle protection. Similar issues prevented the use of metallic-intermetallic laminates in ballistic applications, as weight and flexibility requirements are severely compromised [6]. Other methods aim to use of polymer fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite laminates for ballistic reinforcement as it allows for a considerable decrease in weight [7]. Comparative studies on polymer based carbon fiber laminates reported better blast impact performance in thermoplastic based ones [8]. Yet these resins' low melting points have restricted thermoplastic resins to consumer goods. Elsewhere, Carbon and glass fibers reinforced composites are materials where multifunctionality is desired, given its poor ballistic performance yet exceptional structural properties, highlighted by its high tensile strength, high stiffness, and considerably low strain to failure [9]. By modifying the fiber-matrix interface, multifunctionality can be introduced using sizing techniques [10], and chemical and plasma treatments [11,12] to provide tailored properties and eliminate the need for multi-components protection systems, while satisfying weight, flexibility and cost requirements. However, most of these methods end up damaging the fibers' core and etching its surface, leading to a considerable reduction in the fiber's tensile strength, and thus sacrificing its structural performance for an improvement in its ballistic properties.

Interphase design is a promising approach that exploits the fiber-matrix interface of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites to achieve the desired multifunctionality. By introducing nanomaterials on the fiber's surface, a hierarchical interface is created to provide interfacial reinforcement. The grafting of carbon nanotubes (CNT) onto the surface of carbon fibers have garnered significant interest in recent years due to its unique mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties [13,14]. While it has been shown that CNTs are able to improve ballistic and structural of fiber reinforced composites [15], the high temperatures and catalysts necessary for its synthesis inside chemical vapor deposition (CVD) chambers considerably weakens the fiber by etching it [15]. Other efforts to introduce CNTs into fiber reinforced composites by means of polymer nanocomposites and through mixing it inside the resin. However, adequate dispersion of CNTs inside the resin remains a problem, as the formed agglomerations restricts the integration of such methods into industrial processes [16].

Recently, Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanowires have been demonstrated to be a promising, multi-purpose whiskerization nanomaterial when grafted on the surface of fibers. Arrays of the piezoelectric nanowires are grown on the fiber surface through a hydrothermal (<90°C) aqueous solution based process, thus entirely preserving the fiber strength [17,18]. Galan *et al.* [19] reported a 228% improvement in interfacial strength of carbon fiber reinforced polymers at quasi-static conditions, when optimized ZnO nanowires are grafted to carbon fibers. Under static loading, the ZnO nanowires provide out of plane reinforcement while creating a gradient between the dissimilar fiber and matrix materials, thus, reducing stress concentrations [20]. Malakooti *et al.* [21] found that the addition of a ZnO nanowire interphase to hybrid carbon fiber composites leads to remarkable increase in its damping properties and flexural rigidity, with up to 200% increase in loss factor. Elsewhere, Hwang *et al.* [22,23] reported an increase in interyarn friction of ZnO grown aramid fabric by 23 times, the increase in surface area due to the grafted interphase allows for higher degree of interlocking between ZnO nanowires and material buildup during pullout. Malakooti *et al.* [24] also reported a 66% increase in impact resistance of ZnO grown aramid fabrics with negligible increase in weight. The increase in interyarn friction when ZnO interphase is added reduces the mobility of the yarns within the fabric and results in improved ballistic performance.

In this work, the ability of a ZnO interphase to introduce multifunctionality by concurrently satisfying structural and ballistic interfacial requirements in carbon fiber reinforced composites, while preserving tensile strength, is demonstrated using a recently developed experimental setup. Carbon fibers were initially functionalized using a nitric acid treatment to improve chemical interaction and adhesion

between the fiber's surface and the ZnO interphase. Vertically aligned ZnO nanowires were then uniformly synthesized on the fiber's surface using a hydrothermal reaction. The interfacial properties of the ZnO coated fibers were characterized across various loading rates using a novel single fiber pullout (SFP) experimental setup first reported by Hwang *et al.*[25] that couples a piezoelectric actuator with a discharge circuit that allows up to 10^4 s^{-1} in strain rate and 100 μm in displacement. The tensile strength of the treated fibers was also evaluated using the same setup to ensure no degradation of in-plane properties post-treatment, along with strain rate insensitivity. Post-testing, the pulled-out embedded lengths of ZnO nanowires coated fibers were imaged in order to investigate failure modes. Further experimental work was performed on ZnO nanoparticles interphase in order to study the effect of the interphase's geometry. The obtained results indicate the potential of ZnO nanowires to tailor the fiber-matrix interface of carbon carbon fiber reinforced composites, allowing for the design of lightweight, multifunctional materials with extraordinary performance under both static and dynamic loading conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. Fiber treatment and characterization

AS-4 carbon fibers were received from Hexcel and cleaned in acetone and ethanol successively prior to use. Zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), hexamethylenetetramine ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and zinc acetate dehydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were purchased from Alfa Aesar and used as received. Nitric acid (70%) was used as received from Fisher Scientific. EPON 862 and Epikure curing agent W were received from Momentive Inc. and used as received. The carbon fibers were then functionalized using an oxidative technique in order to substantially increase the oxygen functional groups without any preference to the specific chemistry of the groups [26]. Post-functionalization, the fibers were ultra-sonicated multiple times before drying them at 100 °C for 3 hours. The effect of functionalization on the carbon fibers surface chemistry was quantified using X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) on a Kratos Axis Ultra XPS. All samples were excited by an Al $k\text{-}\alpha$ (1486 eV) monochromatic x-ray source and the resulting data was processed using CASA-XPS.

The seeding of the functionalized carbon fibers was achieved using a ZnO nanoparticles suspension prepared similarly to the one described in Galan *et al.*[19] Individual, functionalized carbon fibers were fixed onto nylon frames and then cleaned sequentially by sonicating in acetone and ethanol for 30 minutes. The frames containing the cleaned fiber were dipped inside the seeding solution and then annealed in a convection oven for 10 minutes at 150 °C. The following process is repeated for three times, before allowing the frame to cool down to room temperature and placing it in an 85 °C preheated solution of 0.001 M $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ and 0.001 M $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in water for 150 minutes. The fibers were then washed with ultra-pure water and methanol in order to remove excess growth solution and any floating ZnO particles, and dried a convection oven for 2 hours. ZnO NPs coated carbon fibers were prepared by only implementing the seeding process. The fibers were imaged using a JEOL 7800 FLV field-emission scanning electron microscope (SEM) to ensure a uniform coating of the fibers' surfaces.

2.2. Mechanical testing

The interfacial shear strength of bare and ZnO coated carbon fibers at varying strain rates, was measured using single-fiber pullout testing. The specimens were prepared by embedding a portion of the carbon fibers inside silicon molds, whose walls were coated with release agent. The embedded lengths were ensured to be less than 100 μm using an optical microscope. The molds were then backfilled with an epoxy mixture of EPON 862 and Curing Agent W at a weight ratio of 100:26.4 and cured at 121 °C for 6 hours. Once fully cured, 5-minutes epoxy (Loctite) was used to add tabs to the free fiber end for testing. Quasi-static single fiber pullout testing was performed using a 5982 series Instron load frame at a cross-head speed of 16 $\mu\text{m/s}$ and samples were examined under an optical microscope to ensure a successful fiber embedded length pullout (Figure 1A). Dynamic single fiber pullout testing was performed using the experimental setup described in Hwang *et al.*[25] at strain

rates of 470 s^{-1} and 2200 s^{-1} (Figure 1B). Similar experimental setups were used to perform tensile tests on bare and ZnO coated carbon fibers. The samples consisted of fibers inserted inside 3.0 mm gauge length cardboard frames and fixed using 5 minutes' epoxy. The failure mechanism during pullout testing was also investigated by imaging the embedded lengths of the pulled out fibers using SEM.

Figure 1: Single fiber pullout experimental setup for: A) Quasi-static loading conditions. B) Dynamic loading conditions

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ZnO coated carbon fiber surfaces were evaluated using SEM imaging. To ensure the accuracy and consistency of the single fiber pullout measurements, it is important that the embedded lengths of tested fibers are sufficiently and uniformly coated with ZnO nanomaterials. The ZnO nanoparticles coated carbon fiber surface can be seen in Figure 2A shows the roughened surface of the carbon fibers after nanoparticle deposition. The 10 nm diameter nanoparticles, initially suspended inside the seeding, solution self-assemble on the carbon fiber to uniformly form a rougher surface. Furthermore, the formed layer can act as a seed layer for the hydrothermal, radial growth of ZnO nanowires (Figure 2B). When inserted inside a growth solution at the designated temperature, the ZnO nanoparticles nucleate into arrays of vertically aligned ZnO nanowires, as the resulting morphology is caused by the the discrepancy of the growth rate between the [0001] polar face and the lateral faces [27]. The grown ZnO nanowires in this study possess an average diameter of $\sim 100 \text{ nm}$ and a length of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 2B shows the dense ZnO nanowires arrays uniformly covering the carbon fiber surface, thus considerably increasing the carbon fibers' surface area and improving its ability to mechanically interlock with the matrix. The morphology of these nanowires, can be controlled by varying parameters such as growth period, and the use of inhibitors [19]. However, it should be noted that the chemical interaction between the synthesized nanowires and the fiber's surface plays a major role in the mechanical performance of the interphase.

Figure 2: Zinc oxide coated carbon fibers. A) Zinc oxide nanoparticles coated carbon fibers. B) Zinc oxide nanowires coated carbon fibers.

The adhesion of ZnO nanowires to the surface of carbon fiber heavily relies on the chemical interaction between both components. Thus, surface functionalization can improve interphase adhesion by populating the fiber's surface with oxygen functional groups. This is primarily achieved using oxidative methods, such as nitric acid oxidation [26]. Characterization of the nitric acid functionalization was performed using XPS, and the C1s spectra for each bare and functionalized carbon fibers were obtained using XPS and a Gaussian distribution fit was performed to each of these groups via a Marquardt regression algorithm with constraints on peaks to determine the best fit. Corrections of less than 2 eV were applied to some of the samples in order to align the main C1s peak at 284.7 eV. Each high-resolution spectrum was first fit with a Shirley background and then decomposed into four components, one for each oxidation state, to fit the data. Fitting was performed with the aid of CASA-XPS using the built in Marquette regression function, with the initial fit starting from the authors' best attempt. Each data set was fit with curves (a Gaussian 70% – Lorentzian 30% mixture, GL30) that were constrained in location and FWHM to realistically model the chemistry of the fiber and capability of the instrumentation, respectively. All peaks had a constrained full width half max (FWHM) of 1.1–1.7 eV, and peaks were constrained at 284.5–285.5 eV, 285.5–287.0 eV, 286.5–288.0 eV, and 288.0–290.0 eV. The residuals of all data at binding energies higher than the main C–C peak were tested for normality with a χ^2 test, assuming an estimated mean and variance, and a 5% confidence level. Table 1 shows an increase in surface oxygen functional groups after functionalization, as the concentration of ketones and carboxyl increase by 5.05% and 3.3%, respectively. The high polarity of ketone groups allows for strong interaction with the Zn ions in the crystal, whereas the lone pairs in hydroxyl or carboxyl groups are either partially shielded by the proton or sterically hindered by the molecule [28]. Therefore, the increase in oxygen polar functional groups on the fiber's surface improves binding between the ZnO NWs and the carbon fiber surface, allowing for enhanced mechanical interlocking between the fibers and the matrix.

Carbon Fiber	% C-C (284.7 eV)	% C-O (286.5 eV)	% C=O (287.8 eV)	% COOH (289.3 eV)
Bare	62.24	25.32	8.2	4.24
Functionalized	53	26.2	13.25	7.55

Table 1: Experimental bonding-state Peak locations and concentrations of the decomposed C1s energy state of bare and functionalized fibers.

The preservation of the tensile properties of carbon fibers post-seeding and growth is a necessary requirement for high composite performance in both structural and ballistic applications. For that, the tensile strength of treated fibers is measured according to ASTM C1557-03 standard at varying strain rates. For any fiber surface treatment to be considered a viable and suitable reinforcement technique, it should be able to retain the composite's in-plane properties, derived from the fibers' axial strength. In addition to the manufacturing defects, oxidative functionalization using chemical solutions can result in fiber surface etching, thus further reducing the fiber's strength. Therefore, post-ZnO NWs growth re-assessment of the fibers' tensile strength is performed. Given the longitudinal deformation through the high strain rate piezoelectric stack is of a maximum of 100 μm , and the strain to failure of carbon fibers at quasi-static loading is typically 1.7%, a gauge length of 3 mm was found suitable for tensile testing across all strain rates. After specimen fabrication, 3 distinct sets of carbon fibers were subjected to quasi-static, intermediate and high strain rate tensile loading, respectively, and the ultimate tensile strength of the fibers was determined. The tensile strength of bare, ZnO nanoparticles, and ZnO nanowires coated carbon fiber were found to remain statistically unchanged across all strain rates (Figure 3). However, the tensile strength of the ZnO nanowires coated fibers were consistently slightly higher than that of both bare and ZnO nanoparticles coated fibers, displaying an increase of 10.2%, 8.4% and 14.5% in tensile strength at strain rates of 0.0016 s^{-1} , 470 s^{-1} , 2200 s^{-1} , respectively. Such findings agree with reported tensile characteristics of various type of fibers when nanomaterials are grafted on their surface [22,24,29]. The observed insensitivity to the applied loading rate is an expected behavior of carbon fibers given the absence of viscoelastic effects. Therefore, it can be concluded that the tensile strength of the carbon fibers is independent of the loading rate and that it is fully conserved after functionalization, seeding, and growth of the ZnO interphase, thus confirming the benign nature of the used fiber treatment.

Figure 3: Tensile strength of bare and ZnO cfibers across various strain rates: Quasi-static strain rate (0.0016 s^{-1}), Intermediate strain rate (470 s^{-1}), High strain rate (2200 s^{-1}).

In addition to the preservation of in-plane properties, the performance of fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites heavily relies on the quality of the fiber-matrix interface. Under quasi-static loading, a strongly adhered fiber-matrix interface is preferred to bridge interfacial discontinuities and improve load transfer between the compliant matrix and the tough fibers. Yet dynamic loading conditions require a weakly adhered fiber-matrix interface in order to allow for the fibers to separate from the matrix, and absorb the impact's energy. The contrasting interfacial behaviors can be achieved through a ceramic ZnO interphase, and can be demonstrated using single fiber pullout testing at various strain rate loading conditions. The SFP at intermediate and high strain rates were performed using the experimental setup described first by Hwang *et al.* [25], which uses a piezoelectric actuator,

along with a discharge circuit that allows for strain rates of up to 10^4 s^{-1} . The embedded length of the single fiber pullout specimen was chosen to be less than $60 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in order to satisfy the actuator's displacement limitations, ensure catastrophic failure of the interface, and avoid frictional effects [30]. Moreover, the embedded fiber length is designed to be considerably larger than the fiber's diameter to avoid Poisson shrinkage and cross-sectional effects. The location of the tabs is another critical parameter as it indicates the fiber's free length, where if not properly designed for, can completely absorbed the actuator's complete displacement and lead to an unsuccessful pullout. Therefore, the fiber's free length needs, at a minimum, to match the difference between the fiber's embedded length and its elastic deformation [31]. The vertical alignment of the fiber's free length at the start of the test is ensured through the application for a pre-load of 0.02 N that was used for all specimens. IFSS is obtained by converting the voltage signal recorded by the piezoelectric dynamic load cell (Figure 4). The trailing and transient oscillations are caused by post-pullout vibrations due to the mass of the grip and have no effect on the voltage signal resulting from the pullout process. The discharge time is also found to be inversely proportional to the applied strain rate.

Figure 4: Dynamic load cell recorded voltage-time response once pullout occurs

The measured IFSS of bare carbon fiber pullout specimens is found to remain relatively constant at approximately 50 MPa across all strain rates. Given that carbon fibers exhibit no stiffening effects and that the mechanical interlocking mechanism between the fiber and the matrix relies mainly on surface roughness, the observed rate independency is expected. However, the IFSS of ZnO nanowires and nanoparticles coated carbon fibers are found to be highly dependent on loading conditions. Relative to bare carbon fibers, and at a quasi-static loading rate of 0.0016 s^{-1} , a maximum increase in IFSS of 87% is observed for ZnO nanowires coated fibers, while a 36% and 54% decrease in IFSS is found at 470 s^{-1} and 2200 s^{-1} , respectively (Figure 5). Similarly, when compared to bare carbon fibers, ZnO nanoparticles coated fibers display a 35% increase in IFSS when quasi-statically loaded, and a 20% and 38% decrease in IFSS when loaded at intermediate and high strain rates, respectively. Added to that, the effect of the interphase's geometry is highlighted by the IFSS of ZnO nanowires coated fibers exceeding that of ZnO nanoparticles coated fibers at a low strain rate, before becoming inferior as loading rate is increased. This decrease in IFSS indicate a weakening of fiber-matrix interface, which is desirable for dynamic loading conditions. At a quasi-static loading rate, the rigid ceramic nanowires are embedded inside the matrix, providing a localized reinforcement gradient and bridging the discrete boundaries of the fiber-matrix interface, thus increasing the IFSS of the composite. However, the effectiveness of the functionally graded interface is reduced as loading rate is increased, resulting in brittle interphase failure and easier fiber-matrix debonding. The change in interfacial properties through a ZnO interphase can be further explained by examining the polymer matrix's behavior with

increasing strain rate. Epoxy-based polymer matrices typically exhibit a strain rate dependent viscoelastic behavior. The elastic modulus of the EPON 862 matrix used here for static and dynamic pullout testing was found to increase by more than 180% when strain rate is increased from 0.0016 s^{-1} to 2200 s^{-1} , going from 3.24 GPa to 9.2 GPa, respectively (Figure 6). Malakooti *et al.*[32] reported that a whiskerized interphase allows for a smooth transition of shear strain inside the pure matrix, thus eliminating high stress concentrations at the level of the fiber-matrix interface. Given the considerable increase in the matrix's elastic modulus with increasing dynamic loading, the ZnO interphase experiences unusual shear loading due to matrix stiffening, and thus leading to brittle failure of the ceramic interphase. This leads to disconnections of the functionally gradient initially provided by the ZnO interphase and results in easier debonding between the fiber and the matrix.

Figure 5: Interfacial shear strength of bare and ZnO coated fibers across various strain rates: Quasi-static strain rate (0.0016 s^{-1}), Intermediate strain rate (470 s^{-1}), High strain rate (2200 s^{-1}).

Figure 6: Elastic modulus of neat EPON 862 epoxy across various strain rates: Quasi-static strain rate (0.0016 s^{-1}), Intermediate strain rate (470 s^{-1}), High strain rate (2200 s^{-1}).

SEM imaging of the embedded portion of the ZnO nanowires coated fibers post-pullout allows for better understanding of the interphase's failure mechanism. Unlike the clean, nanowire-free fiber surface in specimens quasi-statically loaded (Figure 7A), broken ZnO nanowires of up to 40% shorter length are found to remain attached the carbon fiber surface when loaded at high strain rates (Figure 7B). This further confirms the change in interfacial failure as loading rate is increased. Under quasi-static loading, the ZnO nanowires- carbon fiber interface fails, where the ZnO nanowires detach from the fiber surface and remain embedded inside the epoxy matrix as the fiber is pulled out. However, at intermediate and high strain rates, nanowires debonding is preceded by brittle failure resulting in nanowire fracture. This reduces the IFSS of the single fiber composites specimens as loading rate is increased, leading to ZnO interphase being weaker than traditional carbon fiber-matrix interfaces. With that, easier debonding of the fibers from the matrix is achieved, allowing them to carry the load in the cases of impact or ballistic events. It can be then concluded that the brittle failure of the ZnO interphase and nanowires fracture at dynamic loading rates facilitates the release of the fibers from the matrix, and allows for an improved performance of carbon fiber reinforced composites in ballistics and impact applications, while maintaining its reinforcement role under quasi-static loading intact.

Figure 7: SEM images of post-pullout embedded length of ZnO nanowires coated carbon fibers at different strain rates. A) 0.0016 s^{-1} . B) 2200 s^{-1} .

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work has shown the ability to design multifunctional fiber reinforced composites of optimal behavior under both static and dynamic loading conditions by tailoring the fiber-matrix interface. The grafting of zinc oxide interphases on the surface of functionalized carbon fibers helps improve mechanical interlocking between the fiber and the matrix and increases its interaction's surface area, thus improving interfacial shear strength under quasi-static loading conditions. Under dynamic loading conditions, ZnO interphases reduce the IFSS of carbon fiber reinforced composites through its brittle failure, allowing for an enhanced ballistic performance. The ZnO nanoparticles coated carbon fibers displayed up to 58% decrease in IFSS at a high loading strain rate of 2200 s^{-1} , while ZnO nanowires coated carbon fibers exhibited a maximum of 73% decrease in IFSS at similar loading rates. The observed decrease in IFSS under dynamic loading conditions is attributed to the increase in polymer matrix stiffness with increasing strain rates, thus reducing the effectiveness of the interphase's functional gradient, and leading to its brittle failure. Such failure mechanism is desirable in the case of impact and ballistic loading, as the tough fibers possess a better energy absorption performance than the integrity of the composite. This is achieved while preserving the ability of the ZnO interphase to reinforce composites' structural performance. In conclusion, multifunctional carbon fiber reinforced composites, with optimal performance under both static and dynamic loading conditions are made possible through the addition of a ZnO interphase, allowing for the the introduction of lightweight and flexible ballistic protection into structural components.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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